

POLAND

POLAND

IMPROVEMENT OF TEACHING METHODOLOGY OF THE TOPIC “FORMULATION OF OXIDATION-REDUCTION REACTION EQUATIONS” IN SCHOOL CHEMISTRY COURSE USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

Movlonova Sohiba Abdiqodirovna
Mannopova Umida Doniyor qizi

¹ Associate Professor, Department of Chemistry, Nizami
State University of Uzbekistan, acting Ph.D

² Student, Department of Chemistry, Nizami State
University of Uzbekistan,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19182339>

Abstract: This article provides recommendations for teaching students the topic “Formulating equations for oxidation-reduction reactions” in a chemistry course in secondary schools in an easy and simple way, and for using innovative technologies during the lesson.

Keywords: oxidation state, reaction, equalization, oxidation, reduction, innovative education, oxidizing agent, reducing agent.

Based on the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4805 dated 12.08.2020 “On measures to improve the quality of continuous education and scientific efficiency in chemistry and biology”, teachers need to increase their potential in order to further teach chemistry in secondary school textbooks. Therefore, teachers should now organize their lessons not only in the traditional way, but also in an interesting and creative way based on modern innovative technologies, taking into account the age characteristics of students.

We recommend a sample lesson methodology for teaching the chemistry course in secondary schools on the topic “Formulation of oxidation-reduction reaction equations”.

In order to consolidate the previous topic, we will use the “Basket” method to determine the oxidation state of the central atom in complex compounds. In this, students must correctly identify the oxidation states of the central atoms of complex compounds and place them in baskets.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

New topic statement:

Chemical reactions are divided into 2 groups: reactions that occur with a change in oxidation state and reactions that occur without a change in oxidation state. Examples of reactions that occur without a change in oxidation state include:

In this reaction, the oxidation states of none of the elements change. The oxidation state they had before the reaction is the same as the oxidation state they had after the reaction. However, in most chemical reactions, oxidation states change. For example, consider the reaction of water formation.

As we know from our previous lesson, the oxidation states of simple substances are always 0. Oxygen takes one electron from 2 hydrogens, showing an oxidation state of -2. We can give many examples of such reactions. As we know from our previous lesson, the oxidation states of simple substances are always 0. Oxygen takes one electron from 2 hydrogens, showing an oxidation state of -2. We can give many examples of such reactions.

In these reactions, the oxidation states of the elements change.

- Reactions in which the oxidation states of the elements change are called oxidation-reduction reactions.

- In oxidation-reduction reactions, the element or ion that gains electrons is called the oxidizing agent, and the element or ion that loses electrons is called the reducing agent.

- The oxidizing agent is reduced in this chemical process
- The reducing agent is oxidized in this chemical process.

So, in this reaction, the oxidation states of copper and nitrogen changed. Copper changed from an oxidation state of 0 to +2, becoming a reducing agent. Nitrogen changed from an oxidation state of +5 to +4, becoming a reducing agent. You can understand this better by looking at the table below.

Changes in oxidation states of elements.

It gains electrons. Oxidizing (reducing)

Gives electrons. Reducing agent (oxidized)

So, we have identified the oxidizing and reducing agents in this reaction. Now, the number of electrons gained by the oxidizing agent and lost by the reducing agent in the reaction must be equal. To do this, we balance the reaction using the electron balance method.

Based on the numbers 2 and 1 in the equation, the reaction is balanced. The number of all elements on the right and left sides of the reaction must be equal.

Now the reaction has balanced.

We have identified the elements whose oxidation states changed in this reaction.

The reaction is balanced.

Tasks to reinforce the topic:

Balance the following reactions, and write down the oxidizing and reducing agents separately.

1. $\text{NH}_3 + \text{O}_2 = \text{NO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$
2. $\text{KClO}_3 = \text{KCl} + \text{KClO}_4$
3. $\text{S} + \text{KOH} = \text{K}_2\text{S} + \text{K}_2\text{SO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$
4. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH} + \text{O}_2 = \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$

Student Assessment: Students were assessed.

General Conclusion on the topic: Almost all students actively participated in the lesson.

Homework:

1. What are oxidation-reduction reactions?
2. What is an oxidizing agent?
3. What is a reducing agent?
4. What is the electron balance method?

List of used literature:

1. I.R. Askarov, K. Gopirov, N.Kh. Tokhtaboyev 8th grade textbook
2. Abdiqodirovna M. S., Dildora K., Dinora B. MAKTAB KIMYO KURSIDA “YADRO REAKSIYALARI” MAVZUSINI INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA O’QITISH METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH //Shokh Articles Library. – 2025. – T. 1. – №. 2.
3. Abdukodirovna M. S. Methods and their importance in the field of chemistry training //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 11. – C. 382-385.
4. Shomurotova S. X. et al. Improving the Methodology of Teaching the role of metals in Biochemical Processes using Pedagogical Texnologies //Engineering a Management Test. – 2020. – T. 83.

